

1 **Butyrophilin Btn3a2 connects Parp9/14 activation downstream of Xrn1 with XIAP/RIPK2 induction.**

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7 We used a systems biological approach to deciphering mechanism with causative influence in human IBD
8 based on factor identification upstream and downstream of NOD2. Parp9/14 were isolated as
9 common-regulated targets in a transcriptomic discovery approach using multiple IBD-susceptibility genes
10 including NOD2, TRIM22 and XIAP, which revealed Parp9/14 control of the butyrophilins Btn3a2. We
11 demonstrate here that Btn3a2 is associated with a novel MHC class I program whose aligned expression
12 in a network serves as the basis for a mechanism for recognition of self. This self non-self recognition
13 mechanism is likely different from described mechanisms that utilize expression of lymphocyte (Ly)
14 Rhesus (Rh), blood group and transplantation-associated antigens to indicate presence of non-self.
15 Disturbed butyrophilin signaling by BTN3A2 retrieved TNFRSF14, the receptor for LIGHT, a molecule we
16 recently demonstrated was a cardinal Crohn's Disease Montreal B3 phenotype
17 (penetrating/fistulizing-type) susceptibility factor, and whose expression was the major component of a
18 monocyte-macrophage lineage switch associated with transcriptional response to the
19 pathogen-associated molecular pattern muramyl dipeptide (MDP). We demonstrate here a mechanism by
20 which butyrophilin Btn3a2 connects Parp9/14 activation downstream of Xrn1 with XIAP/RIPK2 induction
21 resulting in disease-specific induction of aggressive penetrating disease via *TNFRSF14*.
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